

FRACTURE OF BORON-ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

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Boron-aluminium composite is a typical composite material with a metal matrix and brittle high-modulus fibres. The investigation of its behaviour can be therefore of general interest from the point of view of fracture mechanics of composites.

Two kinds of defects in composites may determine the strength of the material. The first kind is a feature of a structure, that is usually a notch and the cracks of the second kind are considered as a feature of a material and they occur due to breaking of brittle fibres at weak points. Since a high-modulus fibre is usually brittle and the strength along its length is not constant, such breaks make microcracks to be an inherent feature of a composite.

We shall start with the behaviour of the second type of cracks presenting a slightly corrected model of a composite suggested earlier by the authors¹ and some experimental data supported the model. Then we shall

present results of measurements on boron-aluminium specimens. Before that the conditions for correct measurements of the critical coefficient of stress intensity K^* will be investigated.

STRENGTH OF UNNOTCHED COMPOSITE SPECIMENS (THEORY)

Let a material to be composed of the ideal-plastic matrix characterized with the Young modulus E_m , the yield strength σ_m^* , the ultimate strain ϵ_m^* , and of the fibres with the Young modulus E_f . The fibre strength σ_f^* will be assumed to be dependent on flaws distributed randomly along the length. The strength distribution will be that of Weibull, so the distribution density will be

$$g(\sigma) = l\alpha\beta\sigma^{\beta-1}\exp(-l\alpha\sigma^\beta) \quad (1)$$

Here l is the fibre length, α and β are the parameters of the distribution and β is connected with the dispersion only (or with the coefficient of strength variation V_σ)².

When an external load is going up perturbation of the homogeneous stress state of the model occurs because fibres break at weak points. If the local values of fracture toughness is high enough then the break will not grow as a crack. But if the local resistance to the crack extension is not sufficient, the break of a fibre will lead to the break of a neighbour fibre and after that it is necessary to consider the behaviour of a larger crack and to determine again the local value of fracture toughness.

To perform such an analysis one must know how to calculate the local values of fracture toughness of a composite.

In the previous paper¹ the authors used the formula suggested by Kelly and Cooper³ for a composite with rigid fibres and elastic-plastic matrix. In fact this formula gives the contribution of plastic deformation of the matrix to work of fracture of the composite:

$$G'_m = \frac{v_m^2}{v_f} \sigma_m^* e_m^* d \quad (2)$$

Here v_m and v_f are volume fractions of the matrix and the fibres, d is the fibre diameter.

Obviously, Eq.(2) is valid at sufficiently high values of v_f only, when the rigid fibres localize the plastic zone in the vicinity of crack surfaces to the greater extent than the localization around crack tip in the unreinforced matrix. If it is not so, then a more exact approximation to the value of G_m seems to be

$$G''_m = v_m G_m^0 \quad (3)$$

where G_m^0 is the work of fracture of the pure matrix.

Let us assume

$$G_m^0 = \sigma_m^* e_m^* h \quad (4)$$

Here h is the linear dimension related to the size of the plastic zone ahead of the crack tip. The value G_m^0 should be measured in a fracture toughness experiment. Now if $G'_m > G''_m$ then Eq. (3) should be used; if $G'_m < G''_m$ then Eq. (2) is valid. Comparing Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) gives Eq. (3) to be valid at $v_f \leq (1 + h/d)^{-1}$ and Eq. (2) to be valid at $v_f \geq (1 + h/d)^{-1}$. For Durale D16T a reasonable value of G_m^0 should be about 1.4 kgf/mm (see Table 7 on page 269³). The tests carried out on specimens obtained in the same conditions as for the composite

specimens give $\sigma_m^* = 47 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$ and $e_m^* = 0.2$. Hence $h = 0.14 \text{ mm}$, and since $d = 0.10 \text{ mm}$, Eq. (2) is valid in this case at $v_f \geq 0.42$.

At this moment we shall neglect a possible contribution of some mechanisms of the energy dissipation (like interfacial friction between fibre and matrix, and delamination³) to the fracture toughness and take either $G = G'_m$ or $G = G''_m$ depending on volume fraction of fibres. It is important to take into account the fact that because of non-homogeneous fibre distribution in the cross-section of a composite the local values of G in a real composite may depart from the mean value corresponding to Eq. (2) or (3). (Moreover the mean value itself appears to change with the degree of homogeneity of the fibre distribution⁴ but we shall not take into consideration this effect). Some fibres in a composite form bundles and the local values of G within the bundles are close to zero (Fig. 1). A crack once initiating in one fibre of a bundle immediately cuts all fibres of the bundle. Its effective length will therefore be of the order nd .

If it happens at external stress

$$G < G_0 = \sqrt{\frac{(E_f v_f + E_m v_m) G}{\pi n d}} \quad (4)$$

then the crack will be stopped by the matrix and the load may go up.

The first break of a fibre occurs at the weakest point of the whole system of the fibres. The mathematical expectation of the strength of a fibre with the length l according to the Weibull distribution will be

$$\langle \sigma_f^*(l) \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} \sigma f(\sigma) d\sigma = (ld)^{-1/\beta} \Gamma(1+1/\beta) \quad (5)$$

So if l_0 is the single fibre specimen length then it is convenient to use the formula

$$\langle \sigma_f^*(l) \rangle = \langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle (l/l_0)^{1/\beta} \quad (6)$$

Therefore the first break of a fibre in the composite occurs at the mean value of the external stress

$$\langle \sigma^* \rangle = v_f^{1-1/\beta} \left(\frac{l_0}{L} \frac{f}{F} \right)^{1/\beta} \langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle + v_m \sigma_m^* \quad (7)$$

Here L and F are the length and the cross-section of the area of a composite specimen.

Fibre breaking can go on unless the mean length of fibres will be equal to the critical length l_* so as

$$l_*/d = \langle \sigma_f^*(l_*) \rangle / \sigma_m^* \quad (8)$$

At this point the ultimate stress of the composite will be reached and the strength according to the simple Kelly's model³ of a composite with short fibres will be

$$\langle \sigma^* \rangle = \frac{1}{2} v_f \langle \sigma_f^*(l_*) \rangle + v_m \sigma_m^* = \sigma_m^* (1 + \gamma v_f) \quad (9)$$

where the value of γ yields from Eqs.(6) and (8):

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{l_0}{d} \right)^{1+\beta} \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle}{\sigma_m^*} \right)^{\frac{\beta}{1+\beta}} - 1 \quad (10)$$

Now it is convenient to consider fig.2a where stresses corresponding to Eqs. (4), (7) and (9) are plotted.

Here one can see three regions of the volume fractions of fibres - A, B, C, Let us firstly look at the process of loading of a composite in the A - region. At the stress equal to σ_1 fibres begin to break and the breakage continues untill the stress reaches the value of σ_2 when the rupture of the composite takes place because of shears along the interfaces. In a composite from the B - region the breakage begins at the stress σ_1 but the stress can not reach the value of σ_2 since at the stress σ_0 the specimen fractures because of cracks which have been originated during loading from the stress σ_1 to the stress σ_0 . In the C- region the first break of a fibre leads to the complete fracture of a composite.

So at $v_f < v_f^{**}$ (the A - region) the strength of a composite goes up linearly with the volume fraction, at $v_f^{**} < v_f < v_f^{***}$ the mean strength goes down, at $v_f > v_f^{***}$ the strength again goes up.

Let us call the value of v_f equal to v_f^{**} as the critical volume fraction. At supercritical reinforcement, especially at $v_f > v_f^{***}$, a large scatter of the strength of a composite is expected to occur. A significant scale effect is to be expected also.

In fig. 2b it is shown qualitatively how the critical volume fraction v_f^{**} changes with the parameter n which characterizes the degree of homogeneity of the fibre distribution in a composite. Note that if Eq. (2) is taken for the work of fracture and $E = E_f v_f$ (both are sufficiently good approximations at large enough values of v_f), then we shall get

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_m \sqrt{\frac{E_f \sigma_m^* e_m^*}{\pi n}} \quad (11)$$

This obviously lead to

$$v_f = \frac{1 - R}{1 + \gamma R} \quad (12)$$

where

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{\pi n}{e_m^*} \frac{\sigma_m^*}{E_f}} \quad (13)$$

Now before making the comparison with experiments we should say: (1) The model developed has simplified a real situation. Certainly the real behaviour of a composite follows to the dotted line in fig.2c. The transition from one mode of fracture to another occurs slowly through intermixed types. (2) The internal stresses affect the position of the curve I (fig. 2a). In particular, the fibres in a boron-aluminium composite are under compression and the curve I must shift up from the position given by Eq. (7). The permanent stresses in boron-aluminium composite are determined experimentally in⁴. (3) Two of three fracture mechanisms involved in the model, namely the cumulative fracture mode (A in fig.2) and the weakest link-type fracture (C), are well known (see for example⁵). The third mechanism which operates in region B was suggested by the authors in⁴. The main results of the model are the conditions for occurrence of one of the three possible fracture mechanisms.

STRENGTH OF UNNOTCHED BORON- ALUMINIUM SPECIMENS (EXPERIMENTS)

The experiments were carried out on composites with Duralc (DI6) matrix both in aged state (DI6T) and in the state obtained after diffusion bonding (DI6M). The temperature of the process was 485°C and the time was 1.5 h. For DI6M $\sigma_m^* = 32 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$, $e_m^* = 0.065$.

The foil thickness and the winding modulus at a given volume fraction v_f were chosen in such a manner to provide a more or less homogeneous fibre distribution close to hexagonal. The details of the composite testing technique are given in¹. Here we shall present the main result only, namely the dependence of the strength of a composite σ^* on volume fraction v_f (fig. 3) which shows a good enough fit of the experimental data to the theory.

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF BORON'-
ALUMINIUM: EXPERIMENTS AND
ATTEMPTS OF INTERPRETATION

In the model considered above the work of fracture of the matrix determines the behaviour of a composite. In this case a crack size is comparable with the fibre diameter. If a crack is much larger than the fibre diameter then the work of fracture of a composite can be measured in a fracture toughness test based on the linear fracture mechanics. In fact, a number of questions arises with the connection of this procedure. The nature of most of them is of such a sort that the answer can be given only on the experimental basis.

The shapes and sizes of specimens used in the present work are shown in fig. 4. Three types of curves $P - \delta$ (load - crack opening displacement, COD) were obtained in the tests (fig.5). Pop-in on a curve $P - \delta$ does not necessary mean crack advancing in the common sense, it can be related either to fibre breakage in front of the crack tip or microdelamination (or perhaps another processes). So we have always taken a maximum load as a load corresponding to the critical stress intensity coefficient K^* .

The first question to be answered involves the specimen sizes. In previous tests of boron-aluminium⁶ a necessary thickness of a specimen appeared to be less than that for the correct determination of the value of K_{Ic} of usual alloys⁷: the dependence of K^* on the thickness became horizontal after the thickness reached 2.0-2.5 mm. Our results of this kind are given in fig.6. They are obtained on specimens of one type (fig.4B) with a constant $v_f=0.30$ of fibres characterized with a constant mean value of the strength $\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle$ and a constant coefficient of the strength variation V_G . The results obtained are of some interest. At small thicknesses a very large scatter of the experimental data is observed, the mean value of K^* goes up, it reaches maximum at thickness 1.0-1.5mm and then begins slowly to go down. These results together with the data published in⁶ permit, firstly, to take the necessary thickness of the specimens to be about 2.0-2.5mm and, secondly, to correct to some extent results obtained on specimens of different sizes. In fig.7 the influence of the specimen thickness on the crack extension behaviour is illustrated qualitatively.

The next question is about the effect of a crack size on test results. The importance of the relative crack size l/b (b is the specimen width) is shown in⁸. But the value of l/d (d is the fibre diameter, a scale parameter) is expected to be of importance. Some of our experimental data are given in fig.8. They lead to the hypothesis that at $l/d \gg 1$ the value of K^* is independent of l/b . This corresponds to the conclusion of Olster and Jones who tested specimens with $v_f = 0.46-0.50$, $b = 10-15\text{mm}$ and $t = 0.5\text{mm}$. Note that the specimen thickness in their work is in the unfavourable region if we take into account the data

given in fig.6. On the other hand they changed the value of l/b in the wider range and certainly the sharp decrease of the value of K^* with decreasing of l/b to about 0.1 (when the value of l/d reaches 10) can be understood.

The necessity of fatigue preloading of a specimen to make the crack sharper was discussed by Adsit and Witzell⁹ who decided not to do this because of the danger of delamination. On the early stage of the present work some specimens were loaded by pulsating stress to form a visible fatigue crack at the tip of a notch. The values of K^* determined on these specimens were very close to those obtained on the specimens without a fatigue crack. So a main part of the tests was carried out without fatigue preloading.

The main result of the tests is the dependence of the fracture toughness of the composite on the volume fraction of fibres (fig.9).

The comparison of the data given in fig.9a and 9b shows that the fracture toughness of the composite does not depend of the statistical characteristics of fibres (the values of $\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle$ and V_G) in the range indicated on fig.9.

The next conclusion seems to be more important: the value of K^* for the composite goes up with the volume fraction of brittle fibres. What is still more important, the work of fracture G also goes up. The curve $G(v_f)$ is given in fig.10. The values of G are calculated from the measured values of $K^* = \sqrt{CG}$, C being the known combination of the components of the stress tensor (see, e.g. Kelly's book³). We have determined it in an approximate manner^{10,11}. The original point on the curve (the pure matrix) is taken on the known data (Table 7, p269 ref. 3). In fig.10 the

curve $G(v_f)$ calculated from Eqs. (2) and (3) is also plotted. Obviously the work of fracture of the boron-aluminium can not be explained by the plastic deformation of the matrix in the vicinity of the main crack tip. Such explanation should lead to a shortage of the dissipated energy about 4kgf/mm at $v_f = 0.5$.

Four possible hypotheses could be suggested to describe such a discrepancy:

1) The formation of secondary cracks due to the fibre breakage in front of the crack tip at some distances from main crack surfaces (a kind of crack branching). In the vicinity of each fibre break a plastically deformed zone arises and, therefore, the energy dissipates. This process certainly takes place, the evidences can be found in the photographs presented above (fig.7). Obviously, it is necessary to have no less than 8-10 breaks of each fibre ahead of the crack tip to explain the work of fracture of a composite by this mechanism of fracture.

2) Plastic deformation of the matrix along the fibre-matrix interface because of the same fibre breakage process can increase plastically deformed volume of the matrix. In this case

$$\Delta G_m = 4v_f \frac{1}{d} \sigma_m^* e_m^* \delta^2 \quad (14)$$

Here l is the length of plastically deformed zone along fibre, δ is the thickness of this zone around fibre. If the value of l/d for each side of the fracture surface is between 10 and 100, then the value of δ must be between 1 and 10 microns for the value of ΔG_m to be about 4kgf/mm.

3) The friction on the fibre-matrix interface. To estimate the contribution of the friction G_{fm} is

quite difficult. Moreover there is no evidence of pull-out on the microphotographs of the ruptured specimens. But it is still interesting to compare the fracture work of carbon fibre reinforced plastics, which is supposed to be entirely determined by processes going on at the interfaces, and that of boron-aluminium at equal volume fractions of fibres, say, 50%. One may assume that is the case, when fracture toughness of a composite is of the pull-out nature,

$$G_{fm} \propto \frac{\langle \sigma_p^*(l_x) \rangle}{\sigma_n^*} d$$

(Here l_x is a critical fibre length, see, e. g. Kelly's book³). Then the values of G_{fm} for carbon-plastic and boron-aluminium composites appeared to be comparable. For the former case $G_{fm} \approx 0.5 \text{ kgf/mm}$ (see³).

4) Delamination at the interfaces. At the moment it is difficult to estimate the contribution of this process.

Special experiments seem to be necessary to identify a real mechanism (or a combination of the mechanisms) of the energy dissipation in composites.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The interpretation of the two groups of the experimental results presented above will be improper if one tries to use the values of G obtained in the tests of specimens with a large crack ($l/d \gg 1$) in the calculation of the strength of a specimen containing small cracks ($l/d \approx 1-10$) as a result of fibre breakage. Besides the obvious general reasons for such a conclusion we should point out that the extrapolation of the experimental data⁸ to values of values of $l/b \approx 0.05$ gives $K^* = 90 \text{ kgf/mm}^{3/2}$ for the

composite with $v_f=0.5$: it means that for a crack comparable with the fibre diameter one should have $G \approx 0.55$ kgf/mm, that is very close to the pure contribution of the matrix to the work of fracture of the composite (see fig. 10).

So the following conclusions can be formulated :

(1) The experiments carried out on unnotched boron-aluminium specimens support the fracture model of a composite with metal matrix and brittle fibres. The model takes into account non-homogeneous fibre packing in the cross section of the specimen and the possibility of the localization of fibre breaks by the plastic deformation of the matrix. The model permits us to determine the volume fraction v_f^* and v_f^{**} of fibres which correspond to the transitions from one mechanism to another. Within the first range of fibre volume fraction ($0 < v_f < v_f^*$) the cumulative fracture mode takes place, within the second range ($v_f^* < v_f < v_f^{**}$) a partial localization of fibre breaks occurs, and finally, at $v_f > v_f^{**}$ the fracture of the weakest link-type determines the strength of a composite.

(2) The fracture toughness of a composite with a crack much larger than the fibre diameter, is essentially higher than the effective fracture toughness of the matrix which determines the behaviour of the cracks resulting from the breaks of one fibre or fibre bundles within the specimen.

(3) Application of the linear fracture mechanics to the analysis of the composite behaviour of the boron-aluminium type is valid because it is possible to find in an experiment the value of fracture toughness which characterizes the resistance of a material to the crack extension.

(4) At the present there is no model of the composite which would lead to the correct estimation of fracture

toughness of the composite and to optimization of the composite with respect to this parameter.

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Fig.1. A typical fibre packing in the boron-aluminium composite produced by diffusion bonding of fibres and foils.

Fig.2 The dependence of the strength of a composite on the volume fraction of fibres. The curve "0" separates the region of stable cracks with the length nd from the region of fracture stresses. The curve] corresponds to fracture of the weakest link type, the curve 2 corresponds to the cumulative mode of fracture.

Fig.3. The diagram given in fig.2 with the experimental data obtained on boron-aluminium composite with (a) D16T and (b) D16M as matrices.

a)

b)

c)

Fig.4. The specimens used in fracture toughness tests.

Fig.5. Typical curves of load-crack opening displacement.

Fig. 6 The dependence of the measured critical stress intensity coefficients of boron-aluminum on the specimen thickness.

Fig. 7 The fibre breakage ahead of the crack front in boron-aluminium specimens ($v_f = 0.3$).

- a) The first layer of fibres in the specimen with the thickness 1.20mm. The specimen was unloaded when the value $K = 190\text{kgf/mm}^{3/2}$ was reached.
- b) The fourth layer of the specimen with 10 layers ruptured at $K^* = 160\text{kgf/mm}^{3/2}$.
- c) The first layer in the same specimen.

Fig. 8 The dependence of the measured critical stress intensity coefficients of boron-aluminium specimens on the crack length.

○ - $v_f = 0.1$, $t = 2.5$ mm, $\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle = 169$ kgf/mm²,
 $V_\sigma = 0.49$.

▽ - $v_f = 0.4$, $t = 1.35$ mm, $\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle = 169$ kgf/mm²,
 $V_\sigma = 0.49$.

● - $v_f = 0.1$, $t = 1.4$ mm, $\langle \sigma_f^*(l_0) \rangle = 280$ kgf/mm²,
 $V_\sigma = 0.29$

Fig. 9 The dependence of the measured critical stress intensity coefficients of boron-aluminium specimens on the volume fraction of fibres. The thicknesses of the specimens are 2-3mm (o) and 1.0-1.5mm (●).

a) $\langle \sigma_{f1}^*(l_0) \rangle = 280 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$, $V_{\sigma} = 0.29$.

b) $\langle \sigma_{f1}^*(l_0) \rangle = 169 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$, $V_{\sigma} = 0.49$.

Fig. 10 The work of fracture of boron-aluminium as a function of the volume fraction of fibres. The points are obtained in experiments, the dotted line represents the pure contribution of the plastically deformed zone ahead of the front of the main crack.